

Mercury seen from Mars (local Extrema of apparent brightness from 1992-1999)

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2015

An observer stays in a space ship that circles round the Mars.

Explanations: mag = stellar magnitude, °=degree, ' = angular minute, " = angular second

AE= astronomical unit =149598500 km

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance of Mercury from Mars [AE]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	apparent diameter ["]	Distance of Mercury to Sun [AE]
25.1.1992	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.00	1.51-1.52 decreasing	6.7	0.47
7.3.-9.3.1992	-1.00	97-99 increasing	1.70-1.72 increasing	2.55-4.29 decreasing	3.9-4.0 decreasing	0.30-0.32 increasing
13.5.1992	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.99-1.00 increasing	1.95-1.97 decreasing	6.7-6.8 decreasing	0.39-0.40 decreasing
8.6.1992	-0.83	85-88 increasing	1.59-1.62 increasing	8.73-9.30 decreasing	4.1-4.2 decreasing	0.31-0.33 increasing
21.8.1992	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.12	0.32	6.0	0.32-0.33 decreasing
9.9.-12.9.1992	-0.33	70-80 increasing	1.57-1.65 increasing	11.62-12.50 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.34-0.37 increasing
10.10.-18.10.1992	+0.17	96-100 decreasing	1.93-1.97 decreasing	2.82-6.39 increasing	3.4-3.5 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
2.11.-6.11.1992	+0.02	69-78 decreasing	1.64-1.73 decreasing	12.62-13.33 increasing	3.9-4.1 increasing	0.38-0.41 decreasing
26.11.1992	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.26	0.80-0.81 increasing	5.3	0.31
17.12.-21.12.1992	+0.25	68-77 increasing	1.68-1.78 increasing	13.24-13.92 decreasing	3.8-4.0 decreasing	0.40-0.43 increasing
30.12.1992-8.1.1993	+0.31	89-97 increasing	1.93-2.04 increasing	6.26-10.16 decreasing	3.3-3.5 decreasing	0.45-0.47 increasing
7.2.-8.2.1993	-0.22	79-82 decreasing	1.81-1.84 decreasing	9.65-9.88 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.34-0.36 decreasing
1.3.1993	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.32-1.33 decreasing	1.28-1.29 increasing	5.0-5.1 increasing	0.33
10.5.-12.5.1993	-0.46	85-91 decreasing	1.88-1.93 decreasing	6.62-7.73 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.33 decreasing
6.6.1993	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.27-1.28 decreasing	1.23-1.24 increasing	5.2-5.3 increasing	0.38-0.39 increasing
10.8.-12.8.1993	-0.71	93-98 decreasing	1.87-1.91 decreasing	3.59-5.41 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
15.9.1993	weaker than +10.00	<1	1.13	0.25	5.9	0.44
10.11.-12.11.1993	-0.93	99-100 decreasing	1.80-1.81 decreasing	0.32-1.73 increasing	3.7	0.31
2.1.1994	weaker than +7.50	<1	0.98-0.99 increasing	1.87-1.89 decreasing	6.8	0.45-0.46 decreasing
9.2.-11.2.1994	-0.99	94-99 increasing	1.67-1.70 increasing	3.48-5.63 decreasing	3.9-4.0 decreasing	0.30-0.32 increasing
19.4.1994	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.01	1.67-1.69 decreasing	6.6	0.37
12.5.-15.5.1994	-0.75	80-88 increasing	1.56-1.63 increasing	8.93-10.57 decreasing	4.2-4.3 decreasing	0.32-0.34 increasing
28.7.1994	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.15	0.05	5.8	0.32
16.8.-18.8.1994	-0.22	70-77 increasing	1.59-1.66 increasing	12.21-12.72 decreasing	4.0-4.2 decreasing	0.35-0.38 increasing
14.9.-19.9.1994	+0.19	99-100 decreasing	1.98-2.00 decreasing	0.92-3.37 increasing	3.3-3.4 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
10.10.-11.10.	-0.03	73-76	1.70-1.73	12.23-12.46	3.9-4.0	0.38-0.39

1994		decreasing	decreasing	increasing	increasing	decreasing
1.11.1994	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.28	0.93-0.94 increasing	5.2	0.31
25.11.-29.11.1994	+0.34	70-79 increasing	1.73-1.83 increasing	13.12-14.03 increasing	3.7-3.9 decreasing	0.42-0.45 increasing
4.12.-9.12.1994	+0.36	84-91 increasing	1.90-1.99 increasing	9.47-11.71 decreasing	3.5	0.45-0.47 increasing
12.1.-15.1.1995	-0.26	78-86 decreasing	1.81-1.88 decreasing	8.67-9.73 increasing	3.7	0.33-0.36 decreasing
4.2.-5.2.1995	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.32-1.33 decreasing	1.31-1.33 increasing	5.0-5.1 increasing	0.34
15.4.-17.4.1995	-0.51	88-92 decreasing	1.89-1.92 decreasing	6.33-7.09 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.33 decreasing
13.5.1995	weaker than +8.50	<1	1.26	1.14-1.15 increasing	5.3	0.39
16.7.-17.7.1995	-0.76	95-98 decreasing	1.87-1.89 decreasing	3.34-4.52 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
23.8.1995	weaker than +10.00	<1	1.09	0.11	6.1	0.45
15.10.-17.10.1995	-0.96	99-100	1.78-1.79 decreasing	0.86-0.87 increasing	3.7-3.8 increasing	0.31
11.12.1995	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.97	2.12-2.13 decreasing	6.9	0.45
14.1.-17.1.1996	-0.97	92-97 increasing	1.64-1.69 increasing	4.49-6.85 decreasing	4.0-4.1 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
26.3.1996	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.03-1.04 increasing	1.35-1.37 decreasing	6.4-6.5 decreasing	0.35-0.36 decreasing
17.4.-19.4.1996	-0.67	78-85 increasing	1.56-1.62 increasing	10.01-10.93 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.32-0.34 increasing
2.7.1996	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.18	0.2	5.7	0.31
21.7.-25.7.1996	-0.10	67-77 increasing	1.60-1.69 increasing	12.39-13.11 decreasing	4.0-4.2 decreasing	0.39
16.8.-22.8.1996	+0.21	99-100 increasing	2.00-2.02 increasing	1.21-2.16 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
14.9.-16.9.1996	-0.07	71-80 decreasing	1.70-1.78 decreasing	11.28-11.99 increasing	3.8-3.9 increasing	0.36-0.39 decreasing
6.10.1996	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.29	1.04-1.05 increasing	5.2	0.31-0.32 increasing
17.12.-19.12.1996	-0.31	81-86 decreasing	1.84-1.88 decreasing	8.43-9.04 increasing	3.6	0.33-0.35 decreasing
10.1.1997	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.32	1.33-1.34 increasing	5.1	0.35
19.3.-22.3.1997	+0.17	87-95 decreasing	1.87-1.94 decreasing	5.16-7.21 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
18.4.1997	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.23	1.01-1.02	5.4	0.40-0.41 increasing
19.6.-21.6.1997	-0.80	96-100 decreasing	1.85-1.88 decreasing	2.16-4.39 increasing	3.6	0.30-0.32 decreasing
31.7.1997	weaker than +10.50	<1	1.06	0.52-0.53 increasing	6.3	0.46
19.9.-21.9.1997	-0.98	99-100 increasing	1.76-1.77 increasing	0.60-2.00 decreasing	3.8	0.30-0.31 decreasing
18.11.1997	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.97	2.22-2.23 decreasing	6.9	0.43-0.44 decreasing
19.12.-22.12.1997	-0.94	89-95 increasing	1.61-1.67 increasing	5.76-7.83 decreasing	4.0-4.2 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
2.3.1998	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.06	1.02-1.03 decreasing	6.3	0.34-0.35 decreasing
22.3.-25.3.1998	-0.57	74-84 increasing	1.55-1.63 increasing	10.37-11.66 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.33-0.35 increasing
30.4.-3.5.1998	+0.16	89-93 decreasing	1.80-1.84 decreasing	9.74-11.10 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
11.5.-17.5.1998	+0.12	67-79 decreasing	1.57-1.69 decreasing	13.96-15.07 increasing	4.0-4.3 increasing	0.41-0.44 decreasing
8.6.1998	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.20	0.42	5.6	0.31
28.6.-30.6.	+0.01	68-75	1.63-1.70	12.88-13.32	3.9-4.1	0.38-0.40

1998 21.7.-25.7. 1998	+0.24	increasing 98-100 increasing	increasing 2.01-2.04 increasing	decreasing 2.15-4.09 decreasing	decreasing 3.3	increasing 0.47
19.8.-23.8. 1998	-0.11	72-82 decreasing	1.72-1.82 decreasing	10.42-11.49 increasing	3.7-3.9 increasing	0.35-0.38 decreasing
11.9.1998	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.31	1.14-1.15 increasing	5.1	0.31-0.32 increasing
21.11.-24.11. 1998	-0.35	80-89 decreasing	1.84-1.92 decreasing	7.49-8.92 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.35 decreasing
16.12.1998	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.31-1.32 decreasing	1.33-1.34 increasing	5.1	0.35-0.36 increasing
22.2.-24.2. 1999	-0.60	89-96 decreasing	1.87-1.94 decreasing	4.70-6.69 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
25.3.1999	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.20	0.83-0.85 increasing	5.6	0.41-0.42 increasing
25.5.-26.5. 1999	-0.85	98-99 decreasing	1.85-1.86 decreasing	2.27-2.71 increasing	3.6	0.31
9.7.1999	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.03	0.96-0.97 increasing	6.5	0.47
24.8.-26.8. 1999	-0.99	98-100 increasing	1.73-1.75 increasing	0.92-3.37 decreasing	3.8-3.9 decreasing	0.30-0.31 increasing
26.10.1999	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.98	2.17-2.19 decreasing	6.8	0.41-0.42 decreasing
24.11.-26.11. 1999	-0.90	88-92 increasing	1.60-1.64 increasing	7.22-8.49 decreasing	4.1-4.2 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing

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